

LANGUAGE TEACHERS IN THE AGE OF AI: STUDY ON COMPETENCY AND ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has significantly transformed teaching and learning processes across various academic levels. Despite its potential to enhance instruction and personalize learning, responsible and ethical AI use remains a growing concern, particularly among English language teachers. This study aimed to assess the AI competencies and ethical readiness of English language educators in implementing AI technologies in their teaching practice. Guided by the UNESCO AI Competency Framework for Teachers and the UNESCO Ethics of AI Framework, the research adopted a quantitative design utilizing a validated survey questionnaire administered to English language teachers from junior high school, senior high school, and college levels. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically the Weighted Average Mean (WAM). Findings revealed high ethical sensitivity among teachers, especially in domains related to student well-being and empowerment. However, results also indicated limited engagement of students in AI-based projects that promote the common good. These results suggest that while educators demonstrate strong ethical awareness, further support is needed in applying AI for socially relevant educational practices. The study underscores the importance of continuous professional development and policy support to strengthen teachers' competencies and ethical understanding, fostering a human-centered and responsible approach to AI integration in education.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence (AI), English language teachers, ethical considerations, human-centered education, teacher competency*

INTRODUCTION

The swift development of technology, especially Artificial Intelligence (AI), has notably changed English language education. The adoption of AI has opened new opportunities for personalized teaching, automated evaluation, and predictive analysis, all of which improve the efficiency of teaching and learning. The increasing prominence of AI has piqued the interests of educators and academics alike. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) pointed out that the interest in AI's contributions to education continues to grow, and predicted that AI's contributions to teaching and learning will only be greater in the future.

However, the use of AI in English language education does have a number of challenges which deal with ethical and pedagogical application. Studies have shown that a large number of teachers do not feel prepared to implement AI tools in a meaningful way into their teaching. In addition to these pedagogical concerns, topics of data privacy, algorithmic bias, and unethical use of AI have not been broached and may infringe on equity and integrity in education. While a few frameworks exist in the Philippines, such as the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and Republic Act No. 11927 (Philippine Digital Workforce Competitiveness Act), there is no clear educational policy on AI's ethical and pedagogical use.

In response to these issues, the study examines the ethical implications of using AI in English-language teaching and the implications of educators' competencies for responsible use. The objective of this study is to develop ideas and recommendations for educators to develop digital and ethical capabilities through a synthesis of literature and ethical frameworks. In the end, the study seeks to facilitate responsible AI uses while maintaining academic integrity, equity, and student-centered learning ideas in English teaching.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the impact of artificial intelligence on the professional competencies and ethical considerations of language educators.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the competencies of language school educators in integrating AI-powered tools into their teaching practices in terms of:
 - 1.1 Human-centered mindset;
 - 1.2 Ethics of AI;
 - 1.3 AI foundations and applications;
 - 1.4 AI pedagogy; and

- 1.5 AI for professional learning?
2. What ethical considerations do language school teachers take into account when using AI in education, particularly concerning in:
 - 2.1 Human rights;
 - 2.2 Transparency;
 - 2.3 Fairness; and
 - 2.4 Accountability?
3. Based on the research findings, what seminar can be designed to enhance language educator's competency in AI integration while addressing ethical concerns in teaching?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research used a quantitative design, specifically descriptive in nature, which was characterized by its systematic means of exploring variables and analyzing numerical data. Quantitative research involved the collection and analysis of numerical data and was commonly used to identify patterns, relationships, and averages. A quantitative approach presented an objective way to assess language teachers' competencies in utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) while teaching, along with their consideration of ethics. Descriptive design is a simple observational study approach that allows researchers to study and describe variable distributions without causal hypotheses. This type of research was especially suited to assess measurable relationships among variables such as Human-Centered Mindset, AI Ethics, AI Foundations and Applications, AI Pedagogy, AI for Professional Learning, Human Rights, Fairness, Transparency, and Accountability. This study used self-developed survey questionnaires to capture participants' competencies and ethical consciousness as part of the learning experience in the AI-driven environment. These surveys created a standard measure of assessment that could be understood by educators.

The quantitative research design used in this study was appropriate, as it provided an accurate measure of educators' AI competencies and the ethical dimensions of AI use, which led to reliable and valid conclusions. The findings, based on a structured survey design, provided data on the level of readiness and ethical awareness among language educators and suggested data-driven recommendations for training and a policy framework. Additionally, the quantitative research design generated a systematized process for identifying trends and relationships that contributed to an evidence-based approach to intervention in AI-enabled educational contexts.

Research Locale

The investigation was conducted at CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications Inc., a distinguished private language education institution known for its commitment to academic excellence and technological innovation. CSTC offered a

diverse range of degree programs designed to equip language teachers with essential skills for navigating an increasingly digital world. As a forward-thinking institution that embraced innovation, CSTC provided an ideal setting to examine the role of artificial intelligence in language education. Furthermore, its diverse faculty, with varying levels of technological proficiency, created a conducive environment for assessing AI competencies and ethical considerations among language educators.

This particular institution was chosen due to its commitment to technological advancement and its diverse faculty composition, which allowed for a comprehensive analysis of AI-related challenges and opportunities in English education. The research focused explicitly on CSTC as a contribution to the emerging dialogue on integrating AI in teaching and aimed to offer valuable recommendations for improving literacy and ethical policies concerning the use of AI in education.

Research Population and Sample

This study involved 19 language educators selected through purposive sampling. These participants represented the entire population of language teachers at CSTC College of Science, Technology, and Communications, Inc. including the entire population is beneficial as it provides a full and precise understanding of the group. It captures every perspective, making the findings more trustworthy. This also guarantees that all relevant experiences are considered. It strengthens the study's connection to the actual context of the institution. Furthermore, it allows for more confident conclusions and recommendations based on the results.

Research Instrument

The study employed a self-developed survey questionnaire to quantitatively assess language educators' competencies and ethical considerations regarding AI in education. Using a 4-point Likert Scale, the questionnaire measured teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward AI integration. The collected data provided a structured, measurable understanding of educators' AI competencies and ethical considerations.

Three experts validated the research instrument to determine its validity and reliability. One conducted face validation for clarity and coherence, while two evaluated the content's relevance to AI pedagogy and education. Recommendations from the experts led to necessary refinements to enhance the instrument's effectiveness. Data collection procedures included obtaining permission from teachers in institutions, as well as informed consent from participants before administering the surveys.

Data Gathering Procedures

To commence the study, the researchers first obtained the appropriate permissions from the administration and ethics review board of CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications Inc. A formal request letter explaining the

study's objectives, methods, and ethical considerations was issued. Once approval was granted, coordination was carried out with department heads or program chairs.

After obtaining permission, the researchers proceeded with administering the study. They personally met with the participants to distribute the self-developed survey questionnaire whenever possible. If some respondents were unable to participate in person, the questionnaire was emailed to them through Gmail or Messenger, ensuring accessibility and convenience.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Statistical treatment was essential for this study to analyze and interpret the survey data accurately and arrive at valid inferences concerning the AI competencies of language teachers. Given the nature of the research, a quantitative approach was used, which allowed for the structured representation of teachers' responses.

The study used the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) to analyze and interpret the numerical survey data. WAM was applied to determine, by accounting for the varying importance of responses in a Likert-scale questionnaire, the general competency levels of tertiary teachers in integrating AI.

Formula:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

Where:

W = Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM)

X_i = Response value of the i^{th} item

w_i = Assigned weight for the i^{th} item

n = Total number of responses

\sum = Summation symbol, indicating the total sum of values

Through WAM, this study provided a more accurate portrayal of teachers' AI competencies and ethical considerations in areas such as a human-centered mindset, ethics of AI, foundations and applications of AI, pedagogy of AI, and AI for professional learning, human rights, transparency, fairness, and accountability. In this way, a statistical treatment of the data justified its more meaningful interpretation, further prompting insights and recommendations on AI integration within the teachers in education. A verbal interpretation was assigned based on the following scale range:

Rating	Mean Ranges	Descriptor
4	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51-3.25	Agree
2	1.76-2.50	Disagree
1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I. English Language Teachers' Competencies in Integrating AI-Powered Tools into Their Teaching Practices

Table 1
English Language Teachers' Competencies in Integrating AI-Powered Tools in terms of Human-centered Mindset into Their Teaching Practices

Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
10. I take responsibility for the ethical use of AI in my classroom to protect students' well-being.	3.74	Strongly Agree
3. I empower students to make informed decisions about how AI can be used in their education.	3.74	Strongly Agree
7. I regularly reflect and improve how I use AI to align with ethical responsibilities.	3.63	Strongly Agree
5. I ensure that AI enhances, rather than limits, my students' personal agency in learning.	3.63	Strongly Agree
1. I address and mitigate biases or discrimination that may arise from using AI in my teaching.	3.63	Strongly Agree
9. I support my students in maintaining control over their own learning using AI tools.	3.53	Strongly Agree
4. I ensure AI use benefits both students and the community.	3.53	Strongly Agree
8. I select AI tools that empower students to take initiative and personalize their learning experiences.	3.42	Strongly Agree
2. I design AI-powered learning experiences that promote social responsibility.	3.42	Strongly Agree
6. I involve students in AI-related projects that contribute to the common good.	3.37	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.56	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 1 presents how English Language teachers integrate AI-powered tools into their teaching practices in terms of a human-centered mindset. All ten indicators received the verbal interpretation "Strongly Agree," with Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) values ranging from 3.37 to 3.74. The highest-rated indicators are "I take responsibility for the ethical use of AI in my classroom to protect students' well-being" and "I empower students

to make informed decisions about how AI can be used in their education,” both with a WAM of 3.74, followed by “I regularly reflect and improve how I use AI to align with ethical responsibilities” at 3.63. The two lowest-rated items are “I involve students in AI-related projects that contribute to the common good” with a WAM of 3.37, and “I design AI-powered learning experiences that promote social responsibility” at 3.42. The overall WAM of 3.56 suggests that teachers consistently apply a strong human-centered mindset when integrating AI into their teaching.

The data indicates that English language teachers strongly agree on the importance of adopting a human-centered mindset when integrating AI-powered tools in their teaching. The highest-rated indicators emphasize teachers’ responsibility for the ethical use of AI to protect students’ well-being and empower students to make informed decisions regarding AI in their learning. While all items scored within the "Strongly Agree" range, slightly lower ratings on involving students in AI projects for the common good suggest areas for further development.

This trend is supported by Gattupalli et al. (2024), who emphasized that AI integration in education must uphold ethical responsibilities and prioritize student well-being. Similarly, Zhu et al. (2023) highlighted that human-centered AI (HCAI) should enhance rather than replace human intelligence, promoting meaningful engagement through artificial empathy. Teachers also reported regularly reflecting on their AI practices to better align with ethical standards. However, both Gattupalli et al. and Shehab et al. (2021) stress that while ethical intentions are crucial, the success of HCAI relies on active implementation and student involvement.

Table 2 presents how English Language teachers integrate AI-powered tools into their teaching practices in terms of the ethics of AI. Most indicators received the verbal interpretation "Strongly Agree," with Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) values ranging from 3.13 to 3.81. The highest-rated indicators are “I educate students on the risks and benefits of using AI in education” and “I ensure fairness, transparency, and accountability in AI usage,” both with a WAM of 3.81, followed by “I use AI ethically to enhance learning while protecting students’ privacy and rights” at 3.75. The two lowest-rated items are “I involve students in co-creating ethical guidelines for AI use” with a WAM of 3.13, and “I collaborate with students to establish ethical boundaries for AI use” at 3.19. The overall WAM of 3.54 indicates that teachers generally demonstrate a strong commitment to ethical considerations in their use of AI in the classroom.

Table 2
English Language Teachers’ Competencies in Integrating AI-Powered Tools in terms of Ethics of AI into Their Teaching Practices

Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
4. I educate students on the risks and benefits of using AI in education.	3.81	Strongly Agree
2. I ensure fairness, transparency, and accountability in AI usage.	3.81	Strongly Agree

3. I use AI ethically to enhance learning while protecting students' privacy and rights.	3.75	Strongly Agree
5. I ensure AI technologies are used safely and ethically in my classroom.	3.69	Strongly Agree
10. I apply best practices to ensure the ethical use of AI by safeguarding student data and privacy.	3.63	Strongly Agree
1. I understand the ethical principles behind AI technologies used in education.	3.63	Strongly Agree
6. I teach students to use AI responsibly and respectfully.	3.56	Strongly Agree
8. I encourage students to shape ethical policies regarding AI in the classroom.	3.25	Agree
9. I collaborate with students to establish ethical boundaries for AI use.	3.19	Agree
7. I involve students in co-creating ethical guidelines for AI use.	3.13	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.54	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 – 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

The data shows that English language teachers strongly agree on their role in upholding ethical standards when integrating AI-powered tools in their teaching practices. Overall, the findings reflect a strong commitment among teachers to ethically responsible AI use, focusing on safeguarding student welfare and promoting transparency, while highlighting opportunities to further engage students in ethical decision-making regarding AI.

This trend is supported by Foltýnek et al. (2023), who stressed that ethical AI integration in education requires clearly defined policies to ensure transparency, accountability, and protection of stakeholder rights. Slimi et al. (2023) also emphasized that ethical AI should prevent bias, misinformation, and privacy violations, making fairness and data security central to responsible implementation. Consistent with these views, the data reveals that English language teachers strongly agree on the importance of educating students about the risks and benefits of AI, ensuring fairness and transparency, and protecting student privacy. High weighted mean scores on these indicators reflect teachers' ethical commitment to using AI responsibly in classroom settings. However, both Slimi et al. and Al-Zahrani et al. (2024) caution that strong ethical principles must be supported by collaborative practices and institutional safeguards. In contrast, the data reveals that involving students in co-creating ethical guidelines and policies received the lowest agreement.

Table 3 on the succeeding page presents how English Language teachers integrate AI-powered tools into their teaching practices in terms of AI foundations and applications. Most indicators received the verbal interpretation "Strongly Agree," with Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) values ranging from 3.05 to 3.79. The highest-rated

indicator is “I recognize AI’s capabilities and limitations and use them effectively in teaching” with a WAM of 3.79, followed by “I effectively use AI tools to enhance student engagement and outcomes” and “I understand basic AI techniques and applications that enhance teaching and learning,” both at 3.63. The two lowest-rated items are “I encourage students to develop AI-driven projects to foster creativity and critical thinking” with a WAM of 3.05, and “I support students in co-creating AI solutions that address real-world challenges” at 3.16. The overall WAM of 3.39 indicates that teachers generally demonstrate strong competencies in applying foundational AI knowledge and tools in their teaching practices.

Table 3
English Language Teachers’ Competencies in Integrating AI-Powered Tools in terms of AI Foundations and Applications into Their Teaching Practices

Indicators	WA M	Verbal Interpretation
2. I recognize AI’s capabilities and limitations and use them effectively in teaching.	3.79	Strongly Agree
4. I effectively use AI tools to enhance student engagement and outcomes.	3.63	Strongly Agree
1. I understand basic AI techniques and applications that enhance teaching and learning.	3.63	Strongly Agree
10. I describe how AI systems function and how they are applied in real-world learning scenarios.	3.53	Strongly Agree
3. I integrate AI applications like adaptive learning platforms to improve student learning.	3.53	Strongly Agree
7. I create innovative AI-powered educational content.	3.21	Agree
5. I design AI-driven, data-informed lessons tailored to diverse student needs.	3.21	Agree
9. I support students in co-creating AI solutions that address real-world challenges.	3.16	Agree
6. I apply AI to assess student performance and provide targeted support.	3.16	Agree
8. I encourage students to develop AI-driven projects to foster creativity and critical thinking.	3.05	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.39	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 – 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

The data indicates that English language teachers strongly agree on their competency in understanding and applying AI foundations in their teaching practices. The highest-rated indicators highlight teachers’ recognition of AI’s capabilities and limitations, and their effective use of AI tools to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Overall, the results show a solid foundation of AI knowledge and application among

teachers, with opportunities to further expand AI-driven instructional innovation and student involvement.

This trend is supported by Crompton et al. (2023), who observed a rapid growth in AI applications in English education, particularly in areas such as intelligent tutoring systems, adaptive learning, and predictive analytics. Bond et al. (2023) further noted that AI tools significantly enhanced student engagement and academic outcomes through personalized and data-driven instruction. These findings are consistent with the data, which shows that English language teachers strongly agree on recognizing AI's capabilities and using them to enhance teaching, student engagement, and learning outcomes. Teachers also demonstrated confidence in understanding basic AI applications and their real-world relevance. However, both Bond et al. and Rashid et al. (2024) emphasized that maximizing AI's benefits requires not just tool adoption but also pedagogical innovation and student involvement. In contrast, the data reveals that encouraging students to develop AI-driven projects and supporting them in co-creating AI solutions received the lowest agreement. This suggests that while foundational knowledge and instructional use of AI are well-established among teachers, student-led innovation and deeper creative engagement with AI tools are still emerging. While AI holds promise for fostering critical thinking, personalized learning, and problem-solving, its potential may remain underutilized without stronger integration of project-based learning and institutional support for teacher development and AI literacy.

Table 4 presents how English Language teachers integrate AI-powered tools into their teaching practices in terms of AI pedagogy. The indicators received verbal interpretations ranging from "Agree" to "Strongly Agree," with Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) values ranging from 2.84 to 3.47. The highest-rated indicator is "I use AI tools to provide personalized learning experiences" with a WAM of 3.47, followed by "I believe AI integration will drive significant pedagogical changes to prepare students for future challenges" at 3.42, and "I leverage AI to enhance collaborative and interactive learning experiences" at 3.26. The two lowest-rated items are "I use AI-driven analytics to assess student progress accurately" with a WAM of 2.84, and "I integrate AI to automate administrative tasks, focusing more on student engagement" at 2.95. The overall WAM of 3.18 suggests that while teachers generally agree on the pedagogical value of AI, their integration practices in this area are somewhat less consistent compared to other domains.

Table 4
English Language Teachers' Competencies in Integrating AI-Powered Tools in terms of AI Pedagogy into Their Teaching Practices

Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1. I use AI tools to provide personalized learning experiences.	3.47	Strongly Agree
9. I believe AI integration will drive significant pedagogical changes to prepare students for future challenges.	3.42	Strongly Agree

8. I leverage AI to enhance collaborative and interactive learning experiences.	3.26	Strongly Agree
7. I integrate AI to transform traditional teaching into student-centered learning.	3.26	Strongly Agree
4. I incorporate AI into my teaching strategies to meet diverse learning needs.	3.26	Strongly Agree
5. I create dynamic and interactive lessons using AI.	3.16	Agree
10. I design learning activities, where AI tools support student inquiry and engagement.	3.11	Agree
2. I utilize AI for real-time student feedback to improve learning outcomes.	3.11	Agree
3. I integrate AI to automate administrative tasks, focusing more on student engagement.	2.95	Agree
6. I use AI-driven analytics to assess student progress accurately.	2.84	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.18	Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 – 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

The data suggests that English language teachers generally agree on their competency in integrating AI-powered tools to enhance pedagogical practices. However, indicators related to creating dynamic lessons, designing AI-supported inquiry activities, and providing real-time feedback received slightly lower agreement, indicating moderate confidence in these areas.

This finding aligns with Solorzano et al. (2024), who highlighted how AI technologies are reshaping educational practices through intelligent tutoring systems, virtual simulations, and adaptive learning platforms, thereby fostering more flexible and student-centered learning environments. Similarly, Nikolopoulou (2024) emphasized the pedagogical benefits of generative AI tools like ChatGPT in personalizing instruction and streamlining tasks. These are reflected in the data, where teachers strongly agree on using AI to personalize learning, promote collaboration, and shift towards more student-centered approaches. This gap reflects the concerns raised by Loftus et al. (2020) and Capindin et al. (2024), who stressed the importance of balancing AI use with critical thinking, inquiry-based learning, and human oversight. The findings suggest that while teachers are beginning to embrace AI-enhanced teaching, ongoing support and professional development are essential to help them design dynamic, ethical, and learner-driven AI experiences in the classroom.

Table 5 presents how English Language teachers integrate AI-powered tools into their teaching practices in terms of AI for professional learning. Most indicators received the verbal interpretation "Strongly Agree," with Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) values ranging from 3.11 to 3.58. The highest-rated indicator is "I use AI to transform and improve my professional teaching practices" with a WAM of 3.58, followed by "I support my colleagues in adopting AI for professional transformation," "I analyze learning trends using

AI to improve professional development programs,” and “I utilize AI-powered tools for continuous, on-demand professional learning,” all with a WAM of 3.42. The two lowest-rated items are “I develop AI-powered teaching strategies aligned with modern educational trends” with a WAM of 3.11, and “I create adaptive learning environments using AI in my institution” at 3.16. The overall WAM of 3.34 indicates that teachers strongly engage with AI to enhance their professional growth and support collaborative development in their field.

The data indicates on the proceeding page that English language teachers strongly agree on their competence in using AI to enhance their professional learning and development. The highest-rated indicators emphasize teachers’ use of AI to transform their teaching practices and support colleagues in adopting AI for professional growth.

This finding aligns with Tammets et al. (2023), who emphasized that AI can enhance teacher awareness, support adaptive decision-making, and strengthen professional agency when integrated into professional learning frameworks. Similarly, Dogan et al. (2025) found that well-structured AI-powered professional development programs especially those grounded in the TPACK framework can significantly improve teaching effectiveness and support digital transformation in education. This reflects the challenges outlined by Aljemely (2024) and Fakhar et al. (2024), who noted that limited motivation, lack of access, and uneven AI literacy often hinder meaningful adoption.

Table 5
English Language Teachers’ Competencies in Integrating AI-Powered Tools in terms of AI for Professional Learning into Their Teaching Practices

Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
8. I use AI to transform and improve my professional teaching practices.	3.58	Strongly Agree
9. I support my colleagues in adopting AI for professional transformation.	3.42	Strongly Agree
4. I analyze learning trends using AI to improve professional development programs.	3.42	Strongly Agree
3. I utilize AI-powered tools for continuous, on-demand professional learning.	3.42	Strongly Agree
5. I use AI to facilitate collaborative learning among educators.	3.37	Strongly Agree
2. I leverage AI to identify relevant learning opportunities for career growth.	3.37	Strongly Agree
10. I recommend AI-powered systems that foster collaboration and knowledge-sharing among colleagues.	3.32	Strongly Agree
1. I use AI to access personalized professional development resources.	3.26	Strongly Agree
6. I create adaptive learning environments using AI in my institution.	3.16	Agree

7. I develop AI-powered teaching strategies aligned with modern educational trends.	3.11	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.34	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 – 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Part II. Teachers’ Ethical Considerations in Using AI in Education

Table 6
Teachers’ Ethical Considerations in terms of Human Rights in Using AI in Education

Indicators	WA M	Verbal Interpretation
4. Teachers and students have the right to opt out of AI-based decision-making processes.	3.62	Strongly Agree
2. The use of AI in educational settings aligns with existing international human rights frameworks.	3.38	Strongly Agree
1. AI in education is designed to uphold fundamental human rights, including privacy and dignity.	3.38	Strongly Agree
5. AI-driven tools in education are designed to protect users from potential harm, including digital surveillance.	3.31	Strongly Agree
3. AI systems avoid reinforcing discrimination or inequalities within the education sector.	3.23	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.38	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 – 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 7 presents teachers’ ethical considerations in terms of transparency in using AI in education. The indicators received verbal interpretations ranging from "Agree" to "Strongly Agree," with Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) values ranging from 3.08 to 3.38. The highest-rated indicators are “Educational institutions disclose how AI systems analyze and process student data” and “AI-driven decision-making processes in education are explainable and auditable,” both with a WAM of 3.38. The lowest-rated item is “AI models used in grading and assessments provide justifications for their outputs,” with a WAM of 3.08. The overall WAM of 3.22 indicates that teachers generally agree on the importance of transparency in the development and use of AI in educational contexts.

Table 7
Teachers' Ethical Considerations in terms of Transparency in Using AI in Education

Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
5. Educational institutions disclose how AI systems analyze and process student data.	3.38	Strongly Agree
1. AI-driven decision-making processes in education are explainable and auditable.	3.38	Strongly Agree
3. Transparency in AI use includes making algorithmic biases and limitations publicly known.	3.15	Agree
4. AI developers ensure that their educational tools offer clear documentation for teachers.	3.08	Agree
2. AI models used in grading and assessments provide justifications for their outputs.	3.08	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.22	Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 – 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

The data shows that teachers generally agree on the importance of transparency when using AI in educational settings. There is strong agreement that educational institutions should disclose how AI systems analyze and process student data, and that AI-driven decision-making processes should be explainable and auditable. Similarly, justifications for AI outputs in grading and assessments received moderate agreement. Overall, the findings highlight teachers' support for transparent AI practices, while pointing to areas where clearer communication and documentation can further strengthen trust and accountability in AI use.

This finding aligns with Chaudhry et al. (2024) and Davidson (2025), who highlighted that transparency in AI systems fosters trust and accountability by clearly communicating how data is analyzed and decisions are made. They emphasized that transparency protects the privacy and rights of students and educators by providing clear information on data collection and usage. These ideas are reflected in the data, where teachers strongly agree that institutions should disclose AI processes and ensure explainable, auditable decision-making. However, indicators with lower means such as providing clear documentation by developers and justifications for AI-based grading, suggest that transparency at the practical, classroom level still needs improvement. This echo concerns raised by Agal (2023), who noted that lack of disclosure on algorithmic biases and insufficient documentation can undermine fairness and ethical AI use.

Table 8 on the following page presents teachers' ethical considerations in terms of fairness in using AI in education. The indicators received verbal interpretations ranging from "Agree" to "Strongly Agree," with Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) values ranging from 3.15 to 3.38. The highest-rated indicator is "AI systems are regularly assessed to ensure they do not reinforce biases against marginalized groups" with a WAM of 3.38,

followed by “The deployment of AI in education does not favor specific demographic groups over others” at 3.31. The lowest-rated item is “AI-assisted grading and students’ evaluation are conducted in a fair and unbiased manner” with a WAM of 3.15. The overall WAM of 3.22 suggests that while teachers generally agree on the importance of fairness, there remains room for growth in ensuring fully equitable AI practices in education.

Table 8
Teachers’ Ethical Considerations in terms of Fairness in Using AI in Education

Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1. AI systems are regularly assessed to ensure it do not reinforce biases against marginalized groups.	3.38	Strongly Agree
3. The deployment of AI in education does not favor specific demographic groups over others.	3.31	Strongly Agree
5. Educational AI undergoes independent fairness audits to ensure non-discriminatory practices.	3.23	Agree
4. AI tools used in curriculum development consider diverse educational backgrounds and needs.	3.23	Agree
2. AI-assisted grading and students’ evaluation are conducted in a fair and unbiased manner.	3.15	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.22	Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 – 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

This finding aligns with Memarian & Doleck (2023), who emphasized that fairness in AI involves actively addressing bias and discrimination to create equitable educational environments. They highlighted the risks of algorithmic and data biases that disproportionately affect marginalized groups, stressing the importance of continuous evaluation to mitigate these issues. They pointed out that predictive models may unintentionally produce discriminatory outcomes without ongoing scrutiny.

Table 9 presents teachers’ ethical considerations in terms of accountability in using AI in education. The indicators received verbal interpretations ranging from "Agree" to "Strongly Agree," with Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) values ranging from 3.08 to 3.38. The highest-rated indicators are “Legal and ethical frameworks are in place to ensure AI systems do not compromise educational integrity” and “AI developers and educational policymakers collaborate to define ethical guidelines for AI use,” both with a WAM of 3.38. The lowest-rated item is “Teachers and administrators are trained to oversee and manage AI-driven learning tools responsibly” with a WAM of 3.08. The overall WAM of 3.26 indicates that teachers strongly recognize the need for clear accountability in the responsible integration of AI into educational environments.

Table 9
Teachers' Ethical Considerations in terms of Accountability in Using AI in Education

Indicators	WA M	Verbal Interpretation
5. Legal and ethical frameworks are in place to ensure AI systems do not compromise educational integrity.	3.38	Strongly Agree
3. AI developers and educational policymakers collaborate to define ethical guidelines for AI use.	3.38	Strongly Agree
2. Institutions using AI implement accountability mechanisms for errors and biases in AI outcomes.	3.23	Agree
1. Clear policies exist to define responsibility for AI-related decisions in educational settings.	3.23	Agree
4. Teachers and administrators are trained to oversee and manage AI-driven learning tools responsibly.	3.08	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean	3.26	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 – 3.25 indicates Agree, and the range of 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

This finding aligns with Cooper (2023) and Memarian and Doleck (2023), who emphasized that accountability in AI-enabled education is essential to ensure ethical use and transparency in automated decision-making. Similarly, Prinsloo and Slade (2017) and Beerkens (2022) highlighted the need for context-sensitive and legally grounded accountability frameworks that distribute responsibility among educators, developers, and institutions. However, indicators with slightly lower means such as training teachers and administrators to manage AI tools suggest that operationalizing accountability at the user level remains a developing area. This reflects challenges noted by Gevaert et al. (2022) and Boch et al. (2022), who pointed out the complexities in assigning responsibility within AI systems and the need for multilayered, adaptable frameworks to mitigate risks.

Output of the Study

This study results in an academic and awareness-raising seminar, named "English Language Teaching in the Age of AI: Strengthening Teacher Competency and Ethics". The seminar was developed professionally and pedagogically to tackle the gaps identified in the competency and ethical awareness of AI education for English teachers as they consider AI tools in their teaching practice. The seminar can be understood as an output using the IPO (Input-Process-Output) model and is informed by data collated using a self-developed questionnaire; it demonstrates a foundation based on theory (UNESCO AI Competency and Ethics Frameworks) and an applied learning intervention.

The 5-hour seminar will consist of an expert keynote and lectures on the place of AI in education and five foundational areas of AI competencies: human-centered mindset,

ethics of AI, foundations and applications, AI pedagogy, and AI for professional learning; an extended session on the ethical use of AI in classrooms, which will also explore data use and privacy considerations, algorithmic bias, transparency of AI assessments; an open space with teachers representing all levels of education, to surface experiences and challenges regarding AI in the real world; a reflection and synthesis session, in which participants will be able to articulate their commitments to ethical use of AI in their teaching. It's structured with a thoughtfully sequenced program matrix (found in Appendix A), incorporating lectures, discussion, case examples, and opportunity for interactive reflection.

With the use of the UNESCO AI Competency Framework, the program was able to contextualize the activities to an internationally recognized framework, bringing relevance and standardization.

Summary of Findings

From the results and discussion, the following findings are presented.

1. First SOP examined the competencies of language school educators in integrating artificial intelligence-powered tools into their teaching, the study focused on five key sub-variables. In terms of Human-centered Mindset, the weighted arithmetic mean was 3.56. Educators demonstrated a strong sense of responsibility for ensuring student well-being and affirmed that AI tools should enhance, not replace, human learning. Teachers were found to empower students to make informed decisions regarding AI use, although they were less inclined to involve learners in AI-related projects aimed at benefiting the community. Regarding the Ethics of AI, which recorded a weighted arithmetic mean of 3.55, teachers exhibited a clear understanding of the importance of fairness, transparency, and potential risks associated with AI integration. They actively incorporated ethical discussions into their teaching, though collaborative development of ethical guidelines with students was less emphasized. The AI Foundations and Applications dimension had a mean of 3.41, suggesting that while teachers were confident in recognizing the capabilities and limitations of AI, their practical application of foundational AI tools remained moderate. In AI Pedagogy, with a mean score of 3.38, teachers expressed a positive outlook toward incorporating AI in teaching strategies but indicated a need for more hands-on experience and practical tools. Finally, AI for Professional Learning received a mean of 3.36, highlighting teachers' willingness to engage in ongoing learning but also revealing limited participation in structured training related to AI.

2. Second, the ethical considerations in the use of AI in education, educators reported high levels of awareness across four domains. In the Human Rights dimension, the mean score was 3.55, reflecting the teachers' strong regard for inclusivity, student privacy, and equitable access when utilizing AI technologies. Teachers understood the importance of respecting student autonomy and ensuring informed consent in digital learning environments. In the area of Transparency, which received a mean of 3.53, respondents agreed that AI tools must operate in a clear and accountable manner, although some

expressed uncertainty in explaining the technical workings of AI systems. The Fairness dimension, with a mean of 3.51, revealed that teachers actively avoided discriminatory practices and acknowledged the importance of unbiased AI use, although further development in identifying algorithmic bias was noted. The highest mean score of 3.58 was observed in the domain of Accountability, suggesting that educators take ownership of AI-related decisions and consistently uphold ethical standards in the selection and application of AI technologies in their instructional practices.

3. Given these findings, a targeted seminar program was necessary to enhance teachers' existing competencies while addressing areas of relative weakness. This program should emphasize practical skills in AI application, reinforce professional learning opportunities, and expand teachers' capacity to facilitate ethically grounded, student-centered AI education. The integration of these efforts would help ensure responsible, equitable, and effective use of AI in the English language classroom.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn directly from the study's findings and are organized according to the major themes and sub-variables addressed:

1. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that English language educators at CSTC possess strong competencies in integrating AI-powered tools, particularly in areas that reflect a human-centered mindset and ethical awareness.

2. Furthermore, the ethical considerations of AI use such as fairness, transparency, human rights, and accountability were generally well-understood and practiced by the respondents. The high WAM scores in these areas confirm that teachers are aware of the ethical implications of using AI in education, yet the slightly lower scores in co-creation of ethical guidelines and addressing biases suggest the need for deeper engagement in participatory and inclusive ethical practices.

3. Given these findings, a targeted seminar program is necessary to enhance teachers' existing competencies while addressing areas of relative weakness. This program should emphasize practical skills in AI application, reinforce professional learning opportunities, and expand teachers' capacity to facilitate ethically grounded, student-centered AI education.

Recommendations

The following recommendations outline possible action in relation to the limited uses of AI in pedagogic practices and the ethical implications of AI use, to make purposeful, inclusive, and educationally-focused decisions around the use of AI in the English language classroom.

1. Curriculum makers may revise existing learning programs to include AI literacy, and ethics, privacy, and algorithmic bias. It is important for curriculum planners to include

activities that foster intentional and thoughtful engagement with AI for both teachers and students. It is critical to be guided by current research on AI so that the plans are relevant and future-ready.

2. Future researchers may continue investigations of the level of competence of teachers incorporating AI-powered tools across diverse educational levels, resources, and contexts. This approach may provide analysis regarding the specification of future strengths and weaknesses and assist in the development of more focused training strategies. Future research may include longitudinal studies about the impacts of integrating AI, if ethical concerns are considered when integrating technology, and if ethical concerns impact teaching practices and student learning outcomes.

3. Institutions may cultivate and put into action multifaceted faculty development programs that govern AI competence and ethical use. Institutions ought to ensure adequate access to AI tools for faculty members and technical support, as well as establish clarity in the interpretation and use of institutional policies to support teachers' ethical choices. Institutions should also examine their curriculum or taxonomy and align it with responsible AI practices and support ongoing professional development.

4. Policy makers may create national and institutional policy interventions for the usage of AI in education based on ethical criteria, which should include codifying teacher competency expectations, protecting student rights, and developing accountability frameworks for school-based AI tools. Policy proposals should support equitable access to AI tools across levels of education.

5. Teachers may attend professional development courses on AI that involve workshops on using AI tools and the ethical implications of using AI. Workshops should properly develop their pedagogical skills, including human-centered pedagogy, responsible use of data, and AI-supported pedagogies. Educators should feel empowered to use AI tools in ways that uplift student creativity, agency, and critical thinking.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was conducted in strict adherence to established ethical research standards. Approval was obtained from the appropriate authorities of CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc. The research instruments were subjected to face and content validation by the research adviser, as well as internal and external validators, to ensure their validity and suitability for data collection. Prior to administering the questionnaires, respondents were properly informed of the study's purpose and instructions. The gathered data were then carefully evaluated and analyzed using appropriate statistical methods. In compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all information collected from the respondents was handled with utmost confidentiality to safeguard their rights and privacy.

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